

death and decay of old roots. Root dry weight increased from 14 DH to 28 DH, and then declined gradually up to 75 DH. New roots developed 14-28 DH, but they grew very slowly. Plants exhibited roots from the ratoon tillers at 21 DH. Rooting was more profuse and rapid from lower ratoon tillers than from upper tillers. The mean dry weight of roots from ratoon tillers was 11-19% of the total dry weight at 42 DH, ratoon flowering, and harvesting.

Total root dry weight decreased after 28 DH perhaps because main crop roots were decaying as evidenced by 75 to 85% dead roots at ratoon harvest.

Ratoon tiller development in IR44 appears to depend on the main crop root system for nutrients at least up to 21 DH. Thereafter, the requirements were partially supplemented by new roots from ratoon tillers. However, the contribution of new roots seems very low. It is suggested that care be taken to avoid damaging main crop roots at harvest. □

Root production in the ratoon crop of IR44, IRRI.

Effects of N application on rice yield under drought

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We studied the interaction of N and K on rice yield in a field experiment at TNRRI, Sep 1982-Jan 1983 season. Zero, 50, 100, or 150 kg N/ha and 0, 41.5, or 83 kg K/ha with 22 kg P/ha were applied in 3 replications to IR20.

Soil was an Adanur series, very deep, noncalcareous grey brown, clay loam, with sand layers below 110 cm. Soil had pH 6.7, 2.23% organic matter, 0.11% total N, 36.0 meq CEC/100 g, 67.0 kg available P/ha, 0.45 meq exchangeable K/100 g, and 38.9% water-holding capacity.

There was an unusual drought in the Cauvery Delta during the study. We studied the effect of fertilization on rice grown under drought conditions. The crop was irrigated for only 2 wk after transplanting. Drought developed gradually. Surface irrigation was provided

Grain yield of rice under different N fertilization and drought conditions.

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	2.6
50	2.1
100	2.1
150	1.9
CD	0.4

at wide intervals. Water stress was acute from heading to harvest.

Grain yield (mean of three replications) is shown in the table. Under drought conditions, N application considerably decreased yield. There also was a marginal yield decrease with increasing N application. K application did not affect rice yield. □

Evaluation of soil zinc fertility parameters for rice

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We evaluated equilibrium soil-solution Zn concentration in $\mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml}$ (intensity, C), Zn remaining adsorbed on soil in $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$ (capacity, q), Zn supply parameters (unitless unified terms of intensity, capacity, and buffering capacity factors, SP), and corrected supply parameters (unitless new parameter, CSP) at 15° and 30°C and their averages as soil Zn fertility index in a pot experiment.

Twenty Mollisols were equilibrated in duplicate for 2 h with 0.01M CaCl₂ solution (soil solution ratio 1:10) at 15° and 30°C, and C was determined. Using C, q at 15° and 30°C were calculated: $q_{30^\circ\text{C}} = (K_1 \cdot C \text{ at } 30^\circ\text{C}) / (K_2 + C \text{ at } 30^\circ\text{C})$ and $q_{15^\circ\text{C}} = (q_{30^\circ\text{C}} + C \text{ at } 30^\circ\text{C}) - (C \text{ at } 15^\circ\text{C})$, where K₁ was adsorption maxima ($\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$) and K₂ was constant relative to adsorption energy ($\mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml}$). The K₁ = (intercept)⁻¹ and K₂ = (K₁, slope) were estimated for each soil at 15° and 30°C in a separate Zn adsorption study in the range of 5 to 30 μg added Zn/g soil from the equation (Zn adsorbed by soil, $\mu\text{g}/\text{g}$) = $(1/K_1) + (K_2/K_1) \cdot (\text{Zn in solution, } \mu\text{g}/10\text{ ml})^{-1}$. Expected interaction term of intensity, capacity, buffering capacity ($b = (K_2/K_1) \cdot (q_2/C_2)$,

unitless), a better Zn fertility index, SP at 15° and 30°C were calculated: $SP = (q.C)^{1/2} \cdot (K_1 \cdot K_2)^{-1/4}$. Because SP reflected the physicochemically defined soil Zn supply, but not Zn supply to the crop under the influence of Cu, Fe, and Mn, which may compete with Zn at root exchange sites, SPs were corrected to CSP = (SP). $(\sum M_{Zn} \cdot M^{-1} Cu, Fe, Mn)$, where M was μ moles of 0.005M DTPA (pH 7.3)-extractable respective soil nutrients.

Each of 20 soils was used at 5 kg/pot. Twice replicated treatments were 0, 5, 10, or 15 ppm Zn as ZnSO₄. Six 20-d-old Jaya seedlings were grown for 60 d in each of 160 pots, and percent yield was calculated for each soil:

$$\% \text{ yield} = \frac{\text{yield with 0 ppm Zn (g)}}{\text{yield with adequate Zn (g)}} \times 100.$$

Percent yield varied from 73 to 103%. None of C and q at 15° and 30°C and their averages were related to percent yield, showing that neither measure could define Zn fertility (Table 1). Percent yield and SP correlations were not significant because of widely spaced ideal bands of points in plots of percent yield versus SP. Bands merged in an ideal curve in plots of percent yield versus CSP and were significantly correlated, thus emphasizing the need to correct SP. Critical limits of soil Zn as CSP at 15° and 30°C and average CSP were 1.45, 1.27, and 1.17. Because CSPs included a factor of competitive influence of Cu, Fe, and Mn on Zn availability, they appeared to be a potentially better fertility index than SPs.

All CSPs correlated well with Zn concentration in III 1 b, which is normally recommended tissue for analysis of Zn nutrition status (Table 2). In relation to CSP, tissues could be arranged in reliability order for tissue analysis, CSP at 15°: III 1 b > S > III 1 b > 1s, CSP at 30° C: S > III 1 b and average CSP: S > III 1 b > 1s. Zinc concentration in IIb, IV 1 b, R, and WS did not correlate significantly to CSP, thus were unsuitable for tissue analysis. Total Zn uptake correlated significantly with CSP, except CSP at 15°C. Because of the highest correlation coefficient, the CSP at 15°C and analysis of III 1 b were recommended to know Zn status in soils and plants. □

Table 1. Correlation coefficients (r) between percent yield and Zn fertility parameters.

Zn fertility parameters	Range	r
C at 15°C (μ g/10 ml)	0.07-2.74	0.121
C at 30°C (μ g/10 ml)	0.13-0.77	0.122
Average C (μ g/10 ml)	0.13-1.50	0.142
q at 15°C (μ g/g soil)	5.41-30.28	0.056
q at 30°C (μ g/g soil)	5.34-29.70	0.068
Average q (μ g/g soil)	5.37-29.99	0.068
SP at 15°C (unitless)	0.53-4.29	0.237
SP at 30°C (unitless)	0.57-2.76	-0.109
Average SP (unitless)	0.69-2.76	0.129
CSP at 15°C (unitless)	0.32-2.48	0.783*
CSP at 30°C (unitless)	0.35-2.49	0.563*
Average CSP (unitless)	0.42-2.21	0.758*

*Significant at p = 0.05.

Table 2. Correlation coefficients (r) between Zn concentration in rice tissues and significant Zn fertility parameters.

Tissue	r		
	CSP at 15°C	CSP at 30°C	Average CSP
First leaf blade from top (IIb)	0.320	0.370	0.384
Second leaf blade from top (IIIb)	0.534*	0.424	0.438
Third leaf blade from top (III 1 b)	0.790*	0.465*	0.711*
Fourth leaf blade from top (IV 1 b)	-0.051	0.071	0.007
Leaf sheath (1s)	0.446*	0.440	0.507*
Stem (S)	0.593*	0.733*	0.735*
Root (R)	0.022	0.124	0.078
Whole shoot (WS)	0.263	-0.014	0.149
Total Zn uptake in shoot	0.373	0.484*	0.475*

*Significant at p = 0.05.

Effect of applying lac-coated or non-coated urea on rice grain yield

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We compared the efficiency of lac-coated (33% N) and noncoated (46% N) urea in 1981 and 1982 wet seasons. Soil was a clay loam (Typic Aquept) with pH 5.8, 0.63% organic carbon, and electrical conductivity 0.09 mmho/cm. Jaya was planted in poorly drained soil at the Regional Research Station, Semiliguda. There were nine treatments in a randomized block design with four replications. Lac-coated urea was applied at transplanting. Noncoated urea was applied at transplanting, and at 21 and 55d after transplanting (DT). The crop received 60-17-25 kg NPK/ha.

Applying lac-coated urea at 40 kg N/ha at transplanting followed by non-coated urea at 20 kg N/ha at 55 DT sig-

nificantly increased grain yield over other treatments (see table). □

Effect of lac-coated and noncoated urea on grain yield of Jaya, Orissa, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)			
	1981	1982		
Transplanting				
40	20	0	3.8	4.0
40	0	20	4.0	4.3
20	20	20	4.2	4.3
60	0	0	4.0	4.1
40 ^a	20	0	3.9	4.4
40 ^a	0	20	5.1	4.6
20 ^a	20	20	4.5	4.4
60 ^a	0	0	4.4	4.3
Control			3.1	3.2
CD at 5%			0.6	0.2

^a Lac-coated urea.

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